

THE ERA OF TECHNOLOGIES IMPLEMENTED IN EDUCATION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Technology has had a great growth within society, thanks to its implementation it has evolved in various areas from the realization of activities to the implementation of systems that improve processes, as well as improve communication between people through various sources of information that allows them to have a better knowledge of things as well as their environment. With the arrival of technology, various areas and activities have been improved, both social and economic, one of these areas is education, where through the implementation of technological tools and systems it has been allowed to have a greater scope in the learning and teaching of students by being able to implement new study methods that allow them to capture more information to be able to develop their skills in a more efficient way and with This can create new sources of knowledge that allow them to grow both personally and professionally. The objective of the article presented is to demonstrate how technology has had a significant impact on educational development that through these new levels of learning have been reached that allows them to have individuals with greater knowledge and greater informed to integrate more efficiently within society, allowing educational systems to evolve in such a way that they generate a greater reach within the population allowing to have a society with greater access to education.

Keywords: education, education system, society, technologies

INTRODUCTION

New technologies have allowed society to evolve in a faster and more efficient way thanks to the implementation of systems and tools that allow the activities and processes carried out to be done more quickly, efficiently, but above all with the use of fewer resources so it has had great relevance in various economic and social sectors. The impact of technologies has had pros and against this is due to the use that they are given what represents a great help for people among the sectors that have had more benefits with the arrival of technology is education which allows generating training on individuals teaching them values and ways of how to behave before their environment, as well as in society since education allows to develop the knowledge and skills that each person possesses in order to know the capacities that each one of them has.

The implementation of technologies in education allows their systems to have a greater reach thanks to the various technological tools that allow a large part of the population to have access to the internet, allowing them to acquire various knowledge through this type of media which reinforces everything learned in person.

The objective of this research is to describes how new technologies allow the development of the educational system to be efficient, since this represents a significant advance in the way of teaching and learning in relation to all subjects related to the subject of education.

METHODOLOGY

The elaboration of this article was made in order to describe those new technologies have had a great impact on the development of educational systems, allowing an adequate evolution in each of them with the implementation of technology which allows greater access to information as well as Obtain greater knowledge for both personal and social growth. With this, a qualitative methodology was used in order to adequately describe the relationship of educational systems with new technologies.

The main objective of qualitative researchers is to make the facts understandable. Traditionally it has been believed that Qualitative Research is a counterpart of Quantitative Research, when in fact the two complement each other if the Researcher can establish from the beginning of his Research the objectives of the same. (Bejarano, 2016).

APPROACH TO EDUCATION SYSTEMS

The issue of education has had great relevance around the behavior of individuals within society either alone or in groups, since through this system adequate training is instilled so that people develop each of their skills through the knowledge acquired, by the various methods of studies and learning that are instilled through education.

Education foresees that individual have an appropriate behavior before their environment, where respect and values are an essential part of their growth this to have a society in harmony where there is well-being and professional growth both for their own benefit and for that of others, as mentioned by Sáez (2019), Regarding teaching and learning from a social theme:

Since the origin of humanity, the practice of teaching-learning processes has been one of the fundamental pillars for the cognitive, affective and social development of the human species. Even in the womb, a human fetus receives stimuli from its environment.

The values within a society help to have a more harmonious environment where people can understand each other, respecting each other as well as respecting everything they do and what surrounds them, thus creating a more suitable environment for the development of various activities, that is why education has a great impact on the behavior of people since it provides them with the necessary knowledge to be able to develop before society and so that they can grow by themselves.

The educational systems today have had a great diversity of changes both internally and externally, since this type of systems are teaching structures that are made up of schools, as well as organizations that provide sufficient resources to carry out a quality and dignified education.

From the perspective of Solórzano (2019). He presents us with a definition of what the education system is:

It is the organized set of educational services and actions carried out by the State or recognized and supervised by it through the Ministries of Education according to national, provincial or municipal regulations. The education system includes levels of education and other educational services. In turn, these are organized into different educational modalities.

That from another point of view we have the definition of Ensuncho & Almanza (2021). Dnde mention that the education system is:

Social cohesion is fundamental, which will depend almost exclusively on the social, economic and labor context that a country lives, directing its actions to the management and creation of an inclusive system that guarantees education with equity and quality in all actors of the system

Having an educational system allows you to have a better quality in education, the relationship between all the subjects that contribute to education can be carried out allows you to gain the resources and tools necessary for it to develop efficiently, having a significant teaching and learning in the training of individuals involved in education.

EDUCATION THROUGH TECHNOLOGY

The technological era has revolutionized society this because it has facilitated the realization of processes and activities, both in companies, institutions, both public and private organizations as well as helped to improve the daily life of people, thanks to the implementation of technological systems has had a greater reach to various sources of information that are of great relevance for social development as well as presenting tools that allow facilitate daily tasks, saving time and resources, with technology also came the ICTs that are information and communication technologies, since these allow to have a greater scope in the processing of information

The growing presence of ICT in modern society has led education authorities to consider relevant the knowledge, use and incorporation of these technologies in schools. In a similar way to how ICTs are influencing society, altering the principles that have been maintained about communication over time, we can infer that their repercussions affect all social structures, among which the educational system should be highlighted. Lorigo (2005).

The exponential growth that new technologies have presented has caused society to have to adapt to them quickly and constantly since not doing so would imply various factors that can cause a series of problems, not having systems or technological tools that allow a better development in the activity they carry out, That is why adapting to this great change that has arisen with the arrival of new technologies is essential to be able to continue carrying out any type of activity more efficiently.

In the educational field, the implementation of technological systems has caused a greater scope when teaching this thanks to the fact that a large part of society has the appropriate devices to receive

various types of information, which help them obtain greater knowledge allowing them to develop even more each of the skills they possess.

Educational systems seek the most efficient way to structure themselves to provide quality education that can be available to everyone, with the arrival of technology these systems have been adapting to it, making use of various resources that allow them to teach through existing technological tools which generates a greater scope and that people can learn from anywhere at any time, Educational systems have made appropriate use of technology by creating systems and tools that allow them to generate a greater impact on individuals so that they have the possibility of developing their knowledge and thereby obtain greater knowledge in order to create a better society.

It should be noted as mentioned by Correa & De Pablos (2009) that new technologies:

It has been introducing in schools without altering in many cases, the traditional order of its practice and models of knowledge transmission, compatible with many teaching styles and responding to economic interests rather than a renewing intention, using the technologies of tomorrow to manage the curriculum of the past

On the other hand, Cabero et. al. (2003), emphasizes that:

Education cannot be left out of the evolution of new information technologies, and the reason is twofold: On the one hand the new media configure a new society that the educational system will have to serve, and on the other, this system always uses the means used in social communication, and today this happens, inter alia, by the use of telecommunication networks.

New technologies allow to have a more updated educational system, with a greater scope especially due to the growing need of the educational demand that grows day by day in people and this is where the technological tools and systems allow to have that scope to provide a greater education to have a society full of knowledge and with the appropriate skills for its progress.

CONCLUSION

Education is an essential part for social development since this is a training process where individuals learn to develop their skills and knowledge with which they stand out in certain areas within society, in addition to allowing them to have a better interaction before society due to the teaching of values and how to behave in an ethical and professional way before their environment, So it is of great help for social development, representing an important pillar for both personal and group progress.

The fact of using new technologies for the progress of the educational system has provided new paths that education can use, to have greater progress the use of technological tools and systems has had a great scope for learning in students thanks to this you can have a coarser knowledge in various disciplines which help to have greater skills and have greater knowledge, bringing with them better prepared people.

In conclusion, it was possible to describe in a clear and concise way that new technologies have allowed the development of new educational systems, in addition to improving existing ones, allowing them to have a greater scope to various sources of knowledge with which they can develop their skills to be able to grow personally and professionally. , education I have had to adapt to technologies to be able to have a more adequate scope before the new generations which today has a greater knowledge of how to use this type of tools and systems, so the educational systems aim to adapt to these new currents to be able to generate a significant learning and that is available to all.

REFERENCES

- Bejarano, M. A. G. (2016). Qualitative research. *INNOVA Research Journal*, 1(2), 1-9.
<http://201.159.222.115/index.php/innova/article/view/7>
- Cabero Almenara, J., Castaño Garrido, C. M., Cebreiro López, B., Gisbert Cervera, M., Martínez Sánchez, F., Morales Lozano, J. A., ... & Salinas Ibáñez, J. M. (2003). New technologies in university activity. *Pixel-Bit*. (20). <https://redined.educacion.gob.es/xmlui/handle/11162/95441>
- Correa Gorospe, J. M., & De Pablos Pons, J. (2009). New technologies and educational innovation. *Journal of psycho didactics*. 14 (1). 133-145.
<https://addi.ehu.es/bitstream/handle/10810/6521/Rev.%20Psicod.%2014%281%29%20-%20133-145.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Ensuncho Hoyos, C. F., & Almanza Barilla, J. C. (2021). The education system as an essential system for development and social transformation. *Oratores Magazine*. 14 (9), 144-152.
<http://portal.amelica.org/ameli/jatsRepo/328/3282848008/3282848008.pdf>
- Lorido, M. P. (2005). New technologies and education. *Cadernos de Psicopedagogia*, 5(9).
http://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1676-10492005000100007
- Sáez, M. R. (2019). Constructivist education in the digital age. *Journal of Technology, Science and Education*, (12), 111-127. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=6775566>
- Solórzano Robledo, R. (2019). *System, Education, Educational System and Elements of the Mexican Educational System*. [file:///C:/Users/sergio%20tosca/Downloads/DEFINICI%C3%93N%20-%20SYSTEM%20AND%20SYSTEM%20EDUCATION%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/sergio%20tosca/Downloads/DEFINICI%C3%93N%20-%20SYSTEM%20AND%20SYSTEM%20EDUCATION%20(1).pdf)